

Reuven Bar-on View to Exploring Emotional Intelligence

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Abstract

Reuven Bar-on is a Israeli Psychologist who is known for his research and theories on Emotional Intelligence. Bar-on develop a conceptual and psychometric model of Emotional Intelligence (Also known as Emotional and social competencies. He created his model of Emotional Intelligence based on Psychological well being. This model describes EI as an array of Interrelated emotional and social competencies. These competencies are clustered into the five meta factors : Intrapersonal, Interpersonal, Stress Management, Adaptability and General mood. These five meta factors comprise a total of 15 factors e.g. Self Awareness, Assertiveness, Independence, Self Regard, Self Actualization, Empathy, Social Responsibility, Relationship, Reality Testing, Flexibility, Problem Solving, Stress tolerance, Impulse control, Optimism and Happiness.

Key words : Reuven Bar-on, Emotional and Social Competencies, Interpersonal, Intrapersonal, Stress management, Adaptability and General mood.

Introduction :

Emotional Intelligence is a new concept coined by Dainiel Goleman in 1995 in his Book 'Emotional Intelligence : Why it matter than IQ.' But before Goleman, in 1940, Denial Wechsler indicated the non cognitive aspect of general Intelligence. In 1940, another American

Psychologist R.W. Leeper promoted the idea of 'Emotional Thought' or 'Logical Thought.' In 1983, Howard Gardner at Harvard University profound the theory of multiple intelligence. He also focused on 'Intra Psychic Capacities' comprise in Intra-Personal Intelligence and Inter-personal Intelligence.

At the same time Reuven Bar-on conducted a lot of researches and introduced Emotional Quotient as a measure of Emotional Intelligence. He defined Emotional Intelligence as "An Array of Interrelated Emotional and Social competencies that determine How effective Individuals are at understanding and expressing themselves, understanding others and interacting with them as well as coping with daily demands and challenges."

Cognitive abilities to be clear refers the Ability to concentrate the plan to organize materials, to use words and to understand assimilate facts. It means IQ refers individuals personal information bank – Memory, Vocabulary, Visual motor coordination. Some of these obviously contribute to doing well in life, but I.Q. is not a single predictor of success in life. Studies shown that it can serve to predict 1 to 20 percent of success in a given job. History in full of Brilliant, successful men and women who failed miserably or under achieved in the classroom, whose teachers and guidance counselors relegated them to life on the morgen. But despite this convincing body of evidences, society has persisted in believing that success in

school equal success in life. E.Q.-i undeniable evidence has shown about the E.Q. in the success of life.

What is success? It can be define as a ability to set and achieve personal and professional goals what ever they may be. The criteria of success is vary time to time and also vary with the life span. Most of people associate it with the money but it is not a complete meaning of success. More satisfying and rounded definition of the success is related to life satisfaction, happiness, adjustment in pesonal and professional life, social popularity and mental and physical well being.

Thomas Stenly conducted a survey on 733 multi-millionaires in U.S.A. and publish it in a book 'The Millionaire Mind' (Best Selling). In this book, he concluded that the factors that are more responsible for the success, the top five were:

- (i) Being honest with all people.
- (ii) Being well disciplined.
- (iii) Getting along with people.
- (iv) Having a supportive spouse.
- (v) Working harder than the most people.

The above five factors are reflections of emotional intelligence. Cognitive intelligence or I.Q. was 21st on the list and only endorsed by 20% Billionaires.

Another major difference between cognitive and emotional intelligence is that I.Q. is pretty much set. It tend to peak when a person is seventeen, remains constant throughout adulthood. E.Q. however is not fixed. A study in Canada and U.K. concluded that E.Q. rises steadily from the average of 953 and upto 50 it rises 101.5 the same pattern is true for men and women.

The Building Blocks of Emotional Quotient

Reuven Bar-on divided Emotional Intelligence into five areas or Realms and fifteen subsections or scales.

- I. The Intra-personal Realm
- II. The Inter-personal Realm
- III. Adaptability Realm
- IV. Stress Management Realm
- V. General Mood Realm

(I) The Intra-personal Realm :

This realm of Emotional Intelligence concern what we generally refers to as the 'inner self'. It determines How in touch with your feelings you are, How good you feel about yourself and about you are doing in life success, in this area means that you are able to express your feelings, live and work independently, feel strong, and have confidence in expressing your ideas and beliefs. This realm embraces into five sub-scales.

(1) Self-Awareness : It is the ability to recognize your feelings, to differentiate between this to know why you are feeling these feelings? and to recognize the impact of your feelings have on others around you.

(2) Assertiveness : Assertiveness is composed of the three basic components – 2.1 – the ability to express feelings (for example, to accept and express anger, warmth and sexual feelings); 2.2 – the ability to express beliefs and thoughts openly (Being able to voice opinions, disagree, and take a definite stand, even if it is emotionally difficult to do so and even if you have something to loose by doing so); and 2.3 – the ability to standup for personal rights (not allowing others to bother or take advantage of you). Assertive people are not shy – they are able to express their feelings and beliefs (often directly) and thy do so without being aggressive or abusive.

(3) Independence : Independence is the ability to be self directed and self controlled in

your thinking and actions and to be free from emotional dependency. Independent people are self-reliant in planning and making important decisions. They can stand on their own two feet. They may however seek and consider other people's opinions before making the right decisions for themselves in the end; Consulting others is not necessarily a sign of dependency. Independent people are able to function autonomously – they avoid others in order to satisfy their emotional needs. The ability to be independent rests on one's degree of self-confidence and inner strength and the desire to meet expectations and obligations without becoming a slave to them.

(4) Self-Regard : It is the ability to respect and accept yourself as basically good. Respecting yourself is essentially liking the way you are. Self-regard is the ability to appreciate your perceived positive aspects and possibilities as well as to accept your negative aspects and limitations and still feel good about yourself. Its knowing your strengths and weakness, and liking yourself, “Warts to all.” This conceptual component of emotional intelligence is associated with a general feeling of security, inner strength, self-assuredness, self-confidence and feeling of self-adequacy, because individuals with healthy self-regard know their strength and weaknesses and feel good about themselves, they have no trouble openly and appropriately acknowledging when they have made mistakes, are wrong, or don't know all the answers. Feeling some of oneself is dependent upon self-respect and self-esteem, which are based on a fairly well-developed sense of identity. People with good self-regard feel fulfilled and satisfied with themselves at the opposite end of the continuum are feeling of personal inadequacy and inferiority.

(5) Self Actualization : Self-Actualization is the ability to realize your

potential capacities. This component of Emotional Intelligence is manifested by becoming involved in pursuits that leads to a meaningful, rich and full life. Striving to actualize your potential involves developing enjoyable and meaningful activities and can mean a life-long effort and an enthusiastic commitment to long-term goals. Self-Actualization is an ongoing dynamic process of striving towards the maximum development of your ability and talents of persistently trying to do your best and to improve yourself in general. Excitement about your interests energizes and motivates you to continue these interests. Self-actualization is affiliated with feelings of self-satisfaction. Individuals with healthy self-actualization are pleased with the location they find themselves at on life's highway with respect to their personal occupational and financial distinctions.

(II) The Inter-personal Realm :

This realm of Emotional Intelligence concerns what are known as people skills. Those who function well in this area tend to be responsible and dependable. They understand, interact with and relate well to others in a variety of situations. They inspire trust and function well as a part of a team.

(1) Empathy : The ability to be aware of, to understand and to appreciate the feelings and thoughts of others. Empathy is ‘tuning in’ (Being sensitive) to what, how and why people feel and think, the way they do. Being empathetic means being able to “emotionally read” other people. Empathetic people care about others and show interest in and concern for them. It is the ability to non-judgmentally put into words your understanding of the other person's perspective on the world, even if you do not agree with it, or even if you find that perspective ridiculous. Being empathetic shifts an

adversarial relationship to a collaborative relationship.

(2) Social Responsibility : It is the ability to demonstrate that you are a cooperative contributing and constructive member of your social group. This component of Emotional Intelligence involves acting in a responsible manner, even though you might not benefit personally, doing things for and with others, accepting others acting in accordance with your conscience and upholding social rules. Socially responsible people have social consciousness and a basic concern for others and which is manifested by being able to take on community oriented responsibilities. They possess interpersonal sensitivity and are able to accept others and use their talent for the good of the collective, not just the self. People who are deficient in their ability may entertain and social attitudes act abusively towards other and take advantage of others. It doing something for the team, the division, the organization or for society at large that does not benefit you directly.

(3) Inter-personal relationship : This is the ability to establish mutually satisfying relationships that are characterized by intimacy and by giving and receiving affection. Mutual satisfaction includes meaningful social intervenes that are potentially rewarding and enjoyable and characterized by give and take. Positive Interpersonal relationship skill is characterized by sensitivity towards others. This component of Emotional Intelligence is not only associated with the desire to culminate friendly relations with other but with the ability to feel at ease and comfortable in such relations and to possess positive expectations concerning social intercourse.

(III) Adaptability Realm :

This realm of emotional intelligence concerns your ability to size up and respond to a wide range of difficult situations. Success in this area means that you can grasp problems and devise effective solutions, deal with an resolve family issues and meet conflict within your social group and in work place.

(1) Problem Solving : The ability to identify and define problems as well as to generate and implement potentially effective solutions. Problem-solving is multi-phasic in nature and includes the ability to go through a process of (1) sensing a problem and feeling confident and motivated to deal with it effectively; (2) defining and formulating the problem as clearly as possible (e.g. gathering relevant information); (3) generating as many solutions as possible (e.g., brainstorming); (4) making a decision to implement one of the solutions (e.g., weighing the pros and cons of each possible solution and choosing the best course of action); (5) assessing the outcome of the implemented solution; and (6) repeating this process if the problem still exists. Problem-solving is associated with being conscientious, disciplined, methodical and systematic in persevering and approaching problems. This skill is also linked to a desire to do one's best and to confront problems, rather than avoid them.

(2) Reality Testing : The ability to assess the corresponding between whats experienced and what objectively exists. Reality testing involve 'tunning in' to the immediate situation. The best simple-sentence definition of reality testing is that it is the capacity to see things objectively, the way they are rather than the way we wish or fear them to be. Testing this degree or correspondence involves a search for objective evidence to conform, justify and support feelings, perception and thoughts the

emphasis is on pragmatism, objectivity, the adequacy of your perception and authentication of your Ideas and thoughts. An important aspect of this component involve the ability to concentrate and focus when trying to asses and cope with situations that arise. Reality testing is associated with a lack of withdrawal from the outside world, a tuning into the immediate situation, and lucidity and clarity in perception and thought process. In simple terms, reality testing is the ability to accurately “size up” the immediate situation.

(3) Flexibility : The ability to adjust your emotion, thought and behaviour to changing situations and conditions. This component of emotional intelligence applies to your overall, ability to adapt to unfamiliar, unpredictable and dynamic circumstances. Flexible people are agile, synergistic and capable of reacting to change, without rigidity. These people are able to change their mind when evidence suggests that they are mistaken. They are generally open to and tolerant of different ideas, orientation ways and practices, their capacity to shift thoughts and behaviour is not arbitrary but rather in concern with shifting feedback they are getting from their environment. Individuals who lack this capacity tend to be rigid and obstinate. They adopt poorly to new situation and have little capacity to take advantage of new opportunities.

(IV) Stress Management Realm :

This realm of emotional intelligence concerns your ability to withstand stress without coming in, falling apart, losing control or going under. Success in the area means that you are usually calm, rarely impulsive and cope well under pressure. In this work place, these skills are vital if you customarily, face tight deadline or must juggle many demands on your time. At home, they enable you to simultaneously,

maintain a busy household and be mindful of your physical health.

(1) Stress Tolerance : The ability to withstand adverse events and stressful situations without developing physical or emotional symptoms by actively and positively coping with stress. This ability is based on (1) a capacity to choose courses of action for dealing with stress (being resourceful and effective, being able to come up with suitable methods, knowing what to do and how to do it); (2) an optimistic disposition toward new experiences and change in general and toward your own ability to successfully overcome the specific problem at hand; and (3) a feeling that you can control or influence the stressful situation by staying calm and maintaining control. Stress tolerance includes having a repertoire of suitable responses to stressful situations. It is associated with the capacity to be relaxed and composed and to calmly face difficulties without getting carried away by strong emotions. People who have good stress tolerance tend to face crises and problems rather than surrendering to feelings of helplessness and hopelessness. Anxiety, which often results when this component is not functioning adequately, has an ill effect on general performance because it contributes to poor concentration, difficulty in making decisions and somatic problems such as sleep disturbance.

(2) Impulse Control : The ability to resist or delay on impulsive, rive, or temptation to act. Impulse control entails a capacity for identifying your energy and aggression impulses, being composed and putting the brakes on angry, aggressive, hostel and irresponsible behaviour. Problem in impulse control are manifested by low frustration tolerance, impulsiveness, anger control-problems abusiveness, loss of self control and explosive and unpredictable behaviour.

Impulsive people are often described as tempestuous, hot-traded and ‘leap before they look’ people.

(V) General Mood Realm:

This realm of emotional intelligence concern your outlook on life. Your ability to enjoy yourself and others and your overall feeling of contentment or dissatisfaction.

(1) Happiness : The ability to feel satisfied with your life, to enjoy yourself and others and to have fun. Happiness combines self-satisfaction, general contentment and the ability to enjoy life. Happy people often feel good and at ease in both work and leisure; they are able to ‘let their hair down’ and enjoy the opportunities for having fun. Happiness is associated with a general feeling of cheerfulness and enthusiasm. It is a by product and / or barometric indicator of your over all degree of emotional intelligence and emotional functioning. A person who demonstrate a low degree of this component may possess symptoms of depression, such as a tendency to worry, uncertainty about the future social withdrawal, lack of drive depressive thoughts, feeling of guilt, dissatisfaction with life and in extreme cases, suicidal thoughts and behaviour.

(2) Optimism : The ability to look at the brighter side of life and to maintain a positive attitude, even in the face of adversity. Optimism assumes a measure of hope in one’s approach of life. It is a positive approach to daily living. Optimism with opposite of pessimism which is the common symptom of depression.

As a ability Emotional Intelligence play an important role in life success. If a person develop these above competencies, he becomes “star performer” in his/her life. At Multi Health System (M.H.S.) tested the emotional intelligence of 5,00,000 people from over 45 countries. The data were the world’s first to explore the relationship between emotional

intelligence and sex, age, culture, and race. The results concluded that the level of emotional intelligence in the realm’s and subscales highly correlate with the best performance in the various field of life.

As a teacher, Emotional Intelligence in schools is very important. Studies indicate that E.Q. improve teacher performance and adjustment in the classroom and support students to achieve academic excellence.

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